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STUDYING THE STATE OF THE CHILD'S HEALTH DEPENDING ON THE STATE OF THE MOTHER'S HEALTH BY MICRONUTRIENT DEFICIENCY

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Abstract: The purpose of the work is to study the state of the child's health depending on the state of the mother's health, taking into account micronutrient deficiency, through questionnaires and a comprehensive examination of the mother's health status, with the subsequent development of an action plan for the provision of medical and social assistance to prevent micronutrient deficiency. A comprehensive assessment of the mother's health status was carried out by questioning 465 mothers and their children in 6 districts of Samarkand region. In mothers during pregnancy, the following were identified: anemia - 67.9%, toxicosis - 64.2%, endangered conditions - 27.3%, increased blood pressure - 25.5%, 57.6% use of various medications - 57.6 %. chronic diseases - 19.4%; during the feeding period the following were noted: they consumed little grain and legume products - 61.2%, vegetables, fruits and herbs - 60%, dried fruits, fruit juices up to 68%, milk and dairy products - 55.8%, meat products - 60.6 %, fish products - 75.6%; frequent consumption of refined sweets - 85.7%, tea up to 100%, and insufficient family wealth in 44.2%, low knowledge of child care in 52.1% of mothers. An action plan consisting of three stages has been developed.

Keywords: micronutrients, deficiency, questioning, "Mother-Child", diagnosis, correction, prevention.

Introduction. At present, it is obvious that adequate nutrition is determined not only by the energy value of food, the balance of the diet in proteins, fats and carbohydrates, but also by the provision of microelements. The biological significance of micronutrients is not always taken into account in medical practice. Micronutrient deficiency in women creates a "double risk" for the fetus and child (Agajanyan N.A., et al. 2013, Kist A.A. et al. 2007). Health of mother and child, incl. the fight against micronutrient deficiency is one of the primary health objectives of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as

evidenced by the announcement of 2016 “The Year of Healthy Mother and Child”, this is also reflected in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers “On further improvement of measures taken in the field of healthy nutrition of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan” No. 102 dated 25.04. 2015, PCM No. 251 dated 08.29.2015 “On approval of the concept and set of measures to ensure healthy nutrition for the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2015-2020”, which states “conducting scientific research on issues of micronutrient deficiency”, “priority conducting fundamental scientific research in studying the causes development of common nutrition-related diseases, studying the prevalence of micronutrient deficiency, anemia, iodine deficiency, etc.”, order of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 352 dated September 2, 2015, order of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 421 dated November 2, 2015 on the implementation of the above PKMRUz.

Irrational feeding in the first weeks and months of postnatal life of children can be one of the reasons for persistent neurological deficits and delays in further physical and neuropsychic development. Deficient conditions in a woman lead to an increased risk of developing deficiency conditions in a child (Legonkova T.I., 2002). According to I.M. Vorontsov (2001) on adaptation disorders and the formation of deviations in the health of children at the stages of postnatal ontogenesis, observations of the relationship between the duration of breastfeeding and a woman’s provision of micronutrients during lactation are provided.

The stability of the chemical composition of human milk is one of the prerequisites for its normal functioning. Accordingly, the content of chemical elements caused by environmental, occupational, climatic-geographical, nutritional factors, somatic or infectious diseases lead to a wide range of disorders in the elemental “portrait” of a person.

The Zarafshan Valley, being the most south-northern area of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is distinguished by specific climatic, environmental and hygienic living conditions for the population, these include the extremely low provision of the population with essential microelements in water, soil and food products (Rasulov S.K., 2019) .

In this regard, the microelement imbalance of infants requires special geocological studies to clarify the indirect relationship between the health status and morbidity of children depending on the health status of the mother and the biogeochemical conditions of the place of residence.

The purpose of the work is to study the state of health of the child depending on the state of health of the mother, taking into account micronutrient deficiency, through a questionnaire and a comprehensive examination of the mother’s health status, with the subsequent development of an action plan for the provision of medical and social assistance for early diagnosis, correction and prevention of micronutrient deficiency,

Material and research methods. A comprehensive assessment of the infants' health status was carried out in conjunction with an assessment of the health status of their mothers through questionnaires. Questionnaires were completed by 465 mothers and their children in 6 districts of the Samarkand region.

Results obtained and discussion. The results of the survey of mothers showed (Fig. 1) that 67.9% of mothers answered the question whether the mother suffered from anemia during pregnancy. By region, this figure was high in Kushrabad, Urgut, Akdarya, Nurabad tumans and Samarkand - 89% , 77%, 78%, 80% and 96%, respectively.

According to the survey, 64.2% of women suffered from toxicosis during pregnancy. Across regions, this figure ranged from 56% to 80% of cases, which indicates a high incidence of toxicosis in pregnant women. The presence of toxicosis in pregnant women may be prerequisites for a violation of the health of children in the peri- and postnatal periods of life, which should be paid attention to.

Threatened conditions during pregnancy were observed in 27.3% of women. Every fourth woman in the region suffers from a risk of miscarriage. The highest percentage of this indicator was observed in the Bulungur and Akdarya tumans of the region (36.6% and 33.3%).

Increased blood pressure in pregnant women was detected in 25.5% of women. This figure in the Nurabad and Bulungur fogs was the highest - 60% and 33.3%. During pregnancy, 50.9% of women suffered from inflammatory diseases (mainly colds and flu).

It is worth paying attention to the indicator that currently, with the development of advertising services, the number of people using medications without permission has increased. According to the survey, 57.6% of pregnant women used various medications, half of whom, without a doctor's recommendations, unauthorizedly used aspirin, citramon, paracetamol, ampicillin and other drugs for headaches. Uncontrolled use of medications during pregnancy leads to serious consequences for the child. From the above it follows that in rural areas the level of culture and medical knowledge of women is low.

Chronic diseases in women were identified in 19.4% of cases. Women more often suffered from chronic diseases such as gastritis, cholecystitis, pyelonephritis, goiter, bronchitis, hepatitis, etc.

Women who consume grain and legume products less than 2-3 times a day account for 61.2% of cases. They mainly consume cereals 1-2 times a week. A small intake of cereals by a nursing mother causes the development of hypogalactia, protein deficiency, and micronutrients in nursing women and their children.

Among lactating women, those who consume little vegetables, fruits and greens are more than 60%. To the question - do you not consume fruits, dried fruits and fruit juices every day, from 60% to 68% of mothers answered "Yes". From the data it becomes clear that most women have polyhypovitaminosis and polyhypomicroelementosis, which can affect the health of a breastfed child.

Based on survey data, one of the national customs revealed the following facts: nursing mothers mainly consume refined sweets such as navat, jam, and granulated sugar. Among the rural population, incorrect

thoughts about the benefits of sweets in “promoting health”, “to increase blood flow”, etc. are preserved, which causes the development of anemia, gastritis, and upper respiratory tract infections on the part of mothers and their children. To the question – do you consume sweets every day? 85.7% of mothers answered “Yes”. Almost all women in Bulungur, Nurabad, Kushrabad, and Zhambay regions consume artificial sweets daily. Our observations have shown that women, from the first days of birth of a child and in the subsequent days of breastfeeding, consume such artificial sweets as navat and granulated sugar. Eating sweets reduces the acidity of gastric juice, reduces appetite, which leads to impaired absorption of macro and microelements and can cause anemia. From these data it follows that almost all women in the village are on a one-sided carbohydrate diet. Our observations have shown that lactating women who often consume artificial sweets experience deficiency anemia, hypovitaminosis and microelementosis, as well as their children - functional digestive disorders, especially intestinal colic, impaired intestinal absorption, predisposition to colds, intestinal infections, etc.

Among breastfeeding women daily those who do not consume milk and dairy products accounted for 55.8%. The standard daily requirement for dairy products for lactating women per day is 500-600 grams.

If there was milk and dairy products in the family, most mothers did not consume dairy products such as cottage cheese, milk porridge, kefir, etc., which is the main reason for the development of deficiency of such macroelements as calcium, phosphorus, sodium, magnesium, etc., and also hypogalactia.

Daily intake of meat products less than 2 times among lactating women in the region was 60.6%. In some fogs this figure was up to 96%. Most mothers ate meat and meat products 2-3 times a week. In the diet of a nursing mother, the amount of meat products per day is 180 grams. Insufficient intake of meat products and meat substitutes leads to various deficiencies (protein, iron, etc.) of the mother and the child, which causes decreased immunity and micronutrient deficiency. Attention should be paid to the fact that nursing mothers from the village consume less fish products per month. According to the survey, 75.6% of lactating women consume fish products less than twice a month. It is known that seafood contains a large amount of essential macro- and microelements - phosphorus, calcium, iron, zinc, etc. and proteins, as well as fat-soluble vitamins - D, K, A and E. In a rational diet, the mother should contain fish products 3 times a day week in the amount of 100 g.

Drinking tea in daily meals is a basic national custom. According to our data, 91% of nursing mothers drink tea daily, and in some cases - 100%. Excessive intake of tea leads to a decrease in the absorption of iron from the intestinal lumen and the dissolution of gastric juice, which causes the development of anemia, impaired intestinal absorption and deficiency conditions.

The health status of mother and child largely depends on social living conditions and material and living conditions. Research has shown that 44.2% of mothers consider the family to be insufficiently wealthy. Over the past 5 years, with the improvement of social security for families, the level of health of the population has increased significantly.

Among 52.1% of mothers surveyed, there is low knowledge of caring for a healthy and sick child. This circumstance is also the main mechanism for delaying physical and psychomotor development, as well as reducing the adaptive capabilities of the body of young children.

Based on the above data, the provision of medical and social care for the protection of motherhood and childhood, taking into account micronutrient deficiency, is as follows: a comprehensive assessment of the health status of mother and child, starting from primary health care, ending with specialized medical institutions, allows us to solve not only medical problems, but also social, environmental and other problems with the subsequent development of preventive measures in target groups.

Based on the results of a comprehensive assessment of the health status of mother and child, taking into account micronutrient deficiency, we have developed an action plan for the provision of medical and social assistance for early diagnosis, correction and prevention of micronutrient deficiency, for maternal health, which consists of three stages:

1. Providing assistance to a woman outside of pregnancy, preparing her for motherhood, improving the work of antenatal clinics, Marriage and Family centers, genetic centers, etc. This includes measures to protect women's health in general, the development of medical genetic centers taking into account micronutrient deficiencies among girls and young families.

Activity:

- Questioning of girls 1 aged 7-18 years (graduates of high schools, lyceums, colleges) for the purpose of early diagnosis of micronutrient deficiency;
 - Among the high-risk group for micronutrient deficiency, correction is carried out with drugs containing micronutrients and prevention - supplementation with drugs containing micronutrients.
 - Promotion of healthy lifestyles;
 - A balanced diet with a limit on refined sugars, animal fats, salt, switching to food products of local natural flora, rich in micronutrients;
 - Organize "future mother" schools in graduating classes of secondary schools, lyceums and colleges and universities with the issuance of certificates to improve the medical knowledge of expectant mothers and young mothers.
2. A set of measures for antenatal fetal protection in antenatal clinics, pregnancy pathology departments, specialized departments, etc. The most active measures are carried out in the first months of pregnancy.

Activity:

- Improve the quality of medical care for pregnant women by conducting prenatal patronage services in primary health care (medical centers, family clinics) with an emphasis on preventing micronutrient deficiency.
 - Organize "young mother" schools in medical institutions, issuing certificates.
3. Intrapartum fetal protection and rational management of childbirth. Includes measures for the safety of obstetric care and the prevention of complications during childbirth.

Thus, from the above it follows that the questionnaire method of interviewing the mother is an effective and simple method in assessing the health status in the "Mother-Child" system in primary health care. Based on the results obtained from the survey, it is possible not only to assess the health status of the mother and child, but also in terms of carrying out preventive measures, as well as further strengthening the health of the younger generation.

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